

Research Article

Trypanocidal potential of *Camellia sinensis* (Green Tea)

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ABSTRACT

In search for new trypanocidal compounds from natural source, methanolic plant extract (MPE) of *C. sinensis* leaves at different concentrations (250-1000 µg/ml) was evaluated against *Trypanosoma evansi* on Vero cell line grown in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) at appropriate conditions. *In vivo* infectivity assessment of incubated extracts and medium with trypanosomes was carried out in mice. *In vitro* cytotoxicity of test extract at concentrations (100-1.56 µg/ml) was carried out on Vero cells. For *in vivo* test, six mice in a group were inoculated with trypanosomes (1x10⁴/ml). Mice were treated with extract at concentrations (12.5-200 mg/kg body weight) of *C. sinensis* leaves intraperitoneally 48 h post on set of parasitaemia. MPE of *C. sinensis* leaves exhibited antitrypanosomal activity both in forms of immobilization and killing of trypanosomes. At 250 µg/ml of the test extract, trypanosomes could not be detected at 4 h of incubation, which was comparable to the standard drug, diminazine aceturate (50 µg/ml,) at 4 h. Trypanosomes counts decreased in concentration and time –dependent manner with significant difference (P<0.05). In infectivity assessment, group of mice inoculated with contents of wells with apparently killed trypanosomes survived while, the other group of mice with reduced trypanosomes died of parasitaemia. Both MPE of *C. sinensis* leaves and diminazine aceturate (Berenil) were cytotoxic to Vero cell line in all concentrations except at 1.56-12.5 and 6.25-1.56 µg/ml. Mice treated with extract had maximum 6 days of survival compared to 3 days of untreated control.

Keywords: Medicinal plant: *Camellia sinensis* leaves, *Trypanosoma evansi*, *In vitro* and *In vivo* Trypanocidal activity, *In vitro* cytotoxicity test

Abbreviations: DMSO, Dimethylsulfoxide, MPE, Methanolic plant extract, DMEM, Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium

INTRODUCTION

Trypanosoma evansi, a flagellate blood protozoan parasite, is one of the devastating trypanosomes in the genus *Trypanosoma* that causes trypanosomiasis in both domesticated and wild animals where the disease thrives (Freiburghaus et al. 1996; Freiburghaus et al. 1997; WHO, 2004). Trypanosomiasis has re-emerged in recent years (Nok and Nock, 2002; WHO, 2004). This has led to increase in mortality of affected animals (WHO, 2004). The current trypanocides (e.g. diminazine aceturate, ethidium, novidium) are being in used for a long time, and are beset with problems such as resistance to trypanosomes at distinct levels, high cost, limited classes of drug choice and non-availability the drugs in certain parts Medicinal plants of Africa (Nok and Nock, 2002).

Medicinal plants have been identified as future sources of trypanocidal compounds. Many plants extracts, fractions and metabolites from medicinal plants have been identified as newer sources of trypanocidal compounds (Freiburghaus et al. 1996; Nok and Nock, 2002; Shaba et al. 2011).

In folk medicine, *Camellia sinensis* has been used in treatment of many diseases such as stress and stomachache (Nadkarni, 1954; Tyler, 1982). Leaf sample of *C. sinensis* contains polyphenols, methylxanthines, essential oils, proteins, vitamins and amino acid. Pharmacologically, *C. sinensis* has been used as antioxidant, anticancer and in treatment of Crohn's disease, peripheral vascular and artery diseases, and skin diseases. (Katiyar et al. 2000; Alice, 1999; Boschmann and Thielecke, 2007). Active constituents such as tannins, flavan-3-ols derivatives such as epicatechin, gallic acid, epigallocatechin, catechingallate, and epigallocatechin gallate have been isolated (Tyler, 1982; Duke and Atchley, 1984).

Based on above mentioned problems of trypanocides and the new waves of trypanosomes causing havoc in animals, *C. sinensis* leaf sample was extracted with methanol and tested for its trypanocidal activity.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Chemicals

Silica gel-G for thin layer chromatography (TLC), solvents (hexane, chloroform, methanol, acetic acid and ethyl acetate) for extraction of plant materials and development/analysis of TLC plates, vanillin for spray, and iodine for detection of bioactive constituents were used which were purchased from E. Merck, India.

2.2. Plant material

C. sinensis leaves at matured stages were collected in the month of September, 2006 from within the Indian Veterinary Research Institute (IVRI) campus at Izatnagar in Bareilly district of Uttar Pradesh state in India, and subsequently were used.

2.3. Preparation of extract

The extraction was carried out according to the method of Stahl (1969). 20 g *C. sinensis* leaves was powdered using laboratory pestle and mortar, and cold extracted with 200 ml of ethanol (analytical grade). Residues obtained were extracted twice in same medium. The filtrates were combined, dried at 37°C and stored at 4°C until used.

2.4. Solvent systems

The following solvent systems were tested to develop the TLC plates according to the method of Stahl (1969).
Chloroform/hexane/acetic acid (50:50:1)
Chloroform/ethyl acetate/acetic acid (50:50:1)
Methanol and chloroform (20: 80)

2.5. Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) plates

Aliquots (0.2 ml) of extract were applied on TLC plates, dried under room temperature and immersed inside the appropriate solvent systems in a glass jar. It was done to detect the presence of bioactive constituents in applied extract. This was also done following the method of Stahl (1969).

2.6. Animals

Swiss albino mice (20-30 g) of either sex were obtained from Animal Research Laboratory Section of Indian Veterinary Research Institute (IVR) Izatnagar, maintained in standard environmental conditions and fed on a standard diet prepared by the institute with water *ad libitum*. Usage of mice in the experiment was strictly guided by laid down rules of committee on Ethics and Cruelty to Animals of the institute.

2.7. Test organism

T. evansi was obtained from the Division of Parasitology, IVRI, Izatnagar and was maintained in the laboratory by serial sub-passages in Swiss albino mice. The strain was routinely tested for virulence following the method of Williamson et al. (1982).

2.8. Parasite count

Counting of parasite was carried out following the method of Lumsden et al. (1973). A number of fields (10-15) of each drop of blood or incubated media and parasites in triplicate were counted using glass slides under inverted microscope (400X). An average mean trypanosomes count was taken as number of trypanosomes per field.

2.9. *In vitro* trypanocidal activity

In vitro trypanocidal activity was carried out with modified method of Oliveira et al. (2004). A Vero cell line (SIGMA) was grown in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) supplemented with 20-40% fetal calf serum (FCS), GIBCO USA and antibiotics (100 iu penicillin, 100 µg streptomycin and 40 µg gentamycin) in 96-wells flat bottom microculture plates (NUNC, Denmark). Each well received 100 µl of DMEM containing 5x10⁵ cells ml⁻¹. Plates were incubated at 37°C under 5% CO₂ for 12h. After the formation of confluent monolayer, the medium was discarded and replaced with a fresh one. Finally, a high parasitaemic blood from mouse was diluted with DMEM to obtain 1x10⁶ parasites ml⁻¹. Suspension (100 ml of medium with parasites) was added at the rate of 1:1 to test MPE of *C. sinensis*, and the plate was incubated under the same conditions mentioned above. The test was repeated at least thrice.

Stock of test MPE of *C. sinensis* leaves was solubilized in 1% dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO). The concentration in the experiment had no deleterious effect by itself on host cells or parasites. 1% DMSO in distilled water was used as control (Young et al. 2000).

2.10. *In vivo* Infectivity assessment

When incubation for anti-trypanosomal activity was completed, contents of wells with reduced and apparently killed trypanosomes from MPE of *C. sinensis* leaves were inoculated (0.1ml mouse⁻¹) into two groups of mice (six group⁻¹) intra-peritoneal, and observed for more than 30 days for parasitemia (Petama, 1964 and Woo, 1971).

2.11. *In vitro* cytotoxicity test

It was done according to the method of Sidwell and Hoffman. (1997). Vero cell line (SIGMA) was grown in DMEM in 96-wells microculture plates without FCS. Each well was seeded with 500,000 cells ml⁻¹ and plates were incubated at 37°C with 5% CO₂ for 48 h. After the formation of confluent monolayer, the supernatant was discarded and replaced with fresh medium. Confluent monolayer of Vero cell lines was treated with serial dilutions (1.56-100 µg ml⁻¹) of MPE of *C. sinensis* of test materials in triplicate and incubated for 72 h consecutively under the same conditions described previously. At 24 h interval, plate was observed under inverted microscope for cytotoxic effects as compared to untreated normal cells that served as control. In each case, after 72 h of incubation, the culture media of the incubated Vero cells was discarded. Adhered cells were stained with a drop of crystal violet in phosphate buffered solution. Plate was then incubated for 24 h at 37°C in ordinary incubator. Plates were later observed under inverted microscope for cytotoxic effects.

2.12. *In vivo* trypanocidal activity of methanolic extract of *C. sinensis*

This was done according to the method of Freiburghaus et al. (1998). Six mice per concentration of extract were inoculated with trypanosomes (1x10⁴ /ml). Mice ((six group⁻¹) were treated with extract at concentrations (12.5-200 mg/kg body weight) of *C. sinensis* leaves intraperitoneally 48 h post on set of parasitaemia. 1% of DMSO was added to the extract and diluted with DMEM. A drop of blood was taken from the tail-end of the mice daily and parasites were counted as previously described.

2.13. Statistical analysis

Results of trypanocidal activity were expressed as mean ± SEM. Statistical analysis was done using Sigma stat (Jandel, USA).

3. RESULTS AND DISUSSION

Extraction

The solvent, methanol, was suitable in extraction of bioactive constituents as observed on TLC plates (plates not shown). Presence of bioactive constituents from MPE of *C. sinensis* leaves was detected on TLC plates. The

solvent used in extraction of *C. sinensis* is comparable to extraction of MPE of *Picrorrhiza korroa* rhizomes on TLC plates (Shaba et al. 2007).

Thin Layer Chromatography Plates Analysis

Solvent system, methanol/chloroform (20:80), was more suitable than other solvent systems tested in the analysis of thin layer chromatography (TLC) plates with applied aliquots of plant extracts. TLC plates (plates not shown) showed different patterns of bioactive constituents of *C. sinensis* leaves, which were subsequently responsible for anti trypanosomal activity. This method is comparable to that used by Freiburghaus et al. (1998) in bioassay-guided isolation of a diasteroisomer of kolavenol from *Entada Abyssinia* active on *T. brucei. rhodesiense* and Shaba et al. 2009 in extraction of *Terminalia belirica* root bark.

In Vitro Trypanocidal Activity

Results of *in vitro* anti-trypanosomal activity of *C. sinensis* leaves are presented in Table 1. Anti-trypanosomal activity varied from immobilization, reduction and killing of trypanosomes at different concentrations used. At a concentration of 250 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, there was drastic reduction and complete killing of trypanosomes occurred at the same concentration (40.00 ± 0.0 to 0.0 ± 0.0) in 4 h of incubation, which is comparable to 4 h of diminazine acetate (Berenil, a standard drug at 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). Anti-trypanosomal activity is comparable to *in vitro* trypanocidal activity of MPE of medicinal plants used in treatment of trypanosomiasis in northern Nigeria at an effective concentration of 8.3 mg ml⁻¹ (Wurochekke and Nok, 2004) and MPE of *Picrorrhiza korroa* rhizomes where trypanosomes were completely killed at 500 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration (Shaba et al. 2007). An average mean parasite count of 37.67 ± 0.58 is statistically critical value. Average mean parasite count from 37.67 ± 0.58 and below was significant between the treatment groups and negative control ($p \leq 0.05$).

In vivo Infectivity Test

Group of mice inoculated with contents of wells with completely killed trypanosomes survived for more than 30 days, while other group inoculated with contents of wells with reduced trypanosomes died of parasitaemia. *In vivo* Infectivity assessment of anti-trypanosomal activity is comparable to anti-trypanosomal effect of the aqueous extract of *Brassica oleracea* and MPE of *Terminalia belirica* dried fruits where inoculated mice with contents of wells with apparently killed trypanosomes survived (Igweh et al. 2002 and Shaba et al. 2009a).

In Vitro Cytotoxicity Test

In vitro cytotoxic effects of MPE of *C. sinensis* leaves and diminazine acetate at same concentrations on Vero cells depicted different effects such as distortion, swelling, sloughing and death of Vero cells compared to negative normal cells in control wells (Table 3). MPE of *C. sinensis* and diminazine acetate were cytotoxic to Vero cells at all concentrations except at 1.56-12.5 and 1.56-6.25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Extract of *C. sinensis* was one level of concentration better than diminazine, the standard drug. This is comparable to *in vitro* cytotoxicity tests of comparative extraction of *Terminalia chebula* dried fruits and methanolic extract of *Vitex negundo* leaves, in which similar cytotoxic effects were observed (Shaba et al. 2007; Shaba et al. 2008).

In vivo Trypanocidal Activity of Methanolic Extract of C. sinensis

Results of *in vivo* trypanocidal activity of methanolic extract of *C. sinensis* leaves at different concentrations were as given in Table 2. Mice treated with extract (200 mg/kg body weight) had maximum 6 days of survival compared to 3 days of untreated control. This result is comparable to trypanocidal activity of *Nuclea latifolia* in which treated mice exhibited decreased in parasitaemia but could not cure them (Madubunyi, 1995).

Gallocatechin gallate and epigallocatechin gallate may be responsible for its trypanocidal activity as both flavonoids have been reported to be most active of all flavonoids identified from *C. sinensis* (Duke and Atchley, 1984).

Results of trypanocidal activity obtained from *in vitro* were not repeated during *in vivo* trials. This may be due to availability of potent amount of active constituents in the extract acting on trypanosomes, ease of active

constituents' degradation and toxic parts of the extract. Perhaps, pure compound(s) of the flavonoids may be more active in trypanocidal activity. For instance, gallic acid-benzenoid may be partly responsible for antitrypanosomal activity of *E. officinalis*. This is because gallic acid was reported to be possessed anti trypanosomal activity (Koide et al.1998).

Also, usage of enhancer will prolong the trypanocidal activity. This is because some isolated active compounds against trypanosomes are easily degradable (Nok and Nock, 2004).

Table 1. *In vitro* trypanocidal activity of methanolic extract of *Camellia sinensis* leaves against *Trypanosoma evansi* on Vero cell line.

Concentration of plant extract in µg/ml	1 h	2 h	3 h	4 h	5 h	6 h	7 h	8 h
12.5	6.667±0.33	13.50±0.43	39.00±0.73	0.0±0.00	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0
25	6.500±0.43	13.50±0.43	30.17±1.25	42.00±1.29	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0
50	6.667±0.33	12.33±0.49	22.50±0.43	32.67±0.61	42.17±0.83	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0
100	6.500±0.43	6.500±0.43	15.33±0.76	24.33±1.09	36.00±0.77	41.67±0.80	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0
200	6.500±0.43	5.667±0.33	8.500±0.43	24.67±0.71	35.50±0.99	40.50±0.43	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0
Diminazen aceturate (50) Positive control	6.167±0.31	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0
Control (Negative control)	6.167±0.31	13.50±0.56	39.50±0.43	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0

Average mean trypanosomes counts from 37.67± 0.58 and below is significant between the treatment groups and negative control. (P ≤ 0.05 to 0.01).

Table 2. *In vivo* trypanocidal activity of methanolic extract of *Camellia sinensis* leaves in mice.

Concentration of test material in mg/kg body weight	Day3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 6	Day 7	Day 8	Day 9	Day 10
12.5	6.667±0.33	13.50±0.43	39.00±0.73					
25	6.500±0.43	13.50±0.43	30.17±1.25	42.00±1.29				
50	6.667±0.33	12.33±0.49	22.50±0.43	32.67±0.61	42.17±0.83			
100	6.500±0.43	6.500±0.43	15.33±0.76	24.33±1.09	36.00±0.77	41.67±0.80		
200	6.500±0.43	5.667±0.33	8.500±0.43	15.33 ±0.53	24.67±0.71	35.50±0.99	40.50±0.43	
Diminazen aceturate (10) Positive control	6.167±0.31	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0
Control (Negative control)	6.167±0.31	13.50±0.56	39.50±0.43					

Table 3. Cytotoxic effect of methanolic extract of *Camellia sinensis* leave on Vero cell line compared to diminazen aceturate (Berenil).

Concentration of test material in µg/ml	Effects of test extract at various periods of incubation (24 h, 48 h, 72 h)						
	<i>Camellia sinensis</i>	Berenil	<i>Camellia sinensis</i>	Berenil	<i>Camellia sinensis</i>	Berenil	Control
100	100%	66.6%	100%	100%	100%	100%	0
50	100%	33.3%	100%	100%	66.6%	100%	0
25	0	0	66.6%	100%	33.3%	100%	0
12.5	0	0	0	0	0	33.3%	0
6.25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3.13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1.563	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Camellia sinensis and diminazine aceturate were toxic to Vero cell line except at Concentrations range of 1.56-12.5 and 1.56-6.5 µg/ml.

CONCLUSION.

Extract of *C. sinensis* at different concentrations demonstrated variant degrees of trypanocidal activity. Isolation of active constituents and coupling it with enhancer will prolong the trypanocidal activity. This can be achieved via bioassay-guided purification of *C. sinensis* leaf sample.

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References

- Alice M (1999). Green tea for remission maintenance in Crohn's disease? *Am J Gastroenterol.* 94:1710.
- Duke JA and Atchley AA (1984). Proximate analysis. In: Christie BR.(ed.). *The handbook of plant science in agriculture.* CRC Press, Inc., Boca Raton, FL.
- Freiburghaus, F, Steck A, Ptander H, Brun R (1998). Bioassay guided isolation of a diastereoisomer of kolavenol from *Entada abyssinica* active on *Trypanosoma brucei rhodesiense*. *J. Ethnopharmacol.* 61:179-183.
- Freiburghaus F, Jonker SA, Nkuna MHN, Mwasumbi LB, Brun R (1997). *In vitro* trypanocidal activity of some rare Tanzanian medicinal plants. *Acta Trop.* 66:79-83.
- Katiyar SK, Ahmad N, and Mukhtar H (2000). Green tea and skin. *Arch Dermatol.* 136:989-94.
- Koide T, Nose M, Ogihara T, Yabo Y and Ohta M (1998). Trypanocidal effect of gallic acid and related compounds. *Planta Medica* 61: 27-30.
- Lumsden WHR, Herbert WJ, and McNeilage GJC (1973). *Techniques with trypanosomes.* Churchill Livingstone, London.
- Madubunyi I I (1995). Antihepatotoxic and trypanocidal activity of *Nuclea latifolia* bark in rats. *J. Herbs Spices and Medicinal Plants* 3: 33-35.
- Nadkarni AK (1954). *Indian Materia Medica, Popular Prakasham, Bombay* 1, 1298.
- Nok JA and Nock I (2002). Transferin coupled azantraquinone enhances the killing effects on trypanosomes. The role of lysosomal mannosidase. *Parasites* 9: 375-379.
- Oliveira BA, Pereira DG, Fernandes AMAP, DeCastro S.L, Souza ARM, Brito AO, DeSouza and Duran N.(2004). Trypanocidal activity of 2-propen-1-amine derivatives on trypomastigotes culture and in animal model parasitol. *Res.* 9: 1125.
- Petana WB (1964). Trypanosomes infection in laboratory animals. *American J. Trop. Med. and Parasitol* 58: 13.
- Shaba P, Pandey NN, Sharma OP, Rao J.R, Singh, RK.(2011). Anti-trypanosomal potential of methanolic extract of *Calotropis gigantea* leaves against *Trypanosoma evansi* and its cytotoxicity. *Intl J. of. Biosource and stress management.* 73: 121-124.
- Shaba P, Pandey NN, Sharma OP, Rao, JR, Singh RK (2007). *In vitro* trypanocidal activity of methanolic extract of *Picrorrhiza kurroa* rhizomes against *Trypanosoma evansi*. *Planta Medica* 73, 997-1034.

- Shaba P, Pandey NN, Sharma OP, Rao JR, Singh RK (2009a). *In vitro* trypanocidal activity of comparative extraction of *Terminalia belirica* dried fruits with solvents of different polarities against *Trypanosoma evansi*. The Internet J. Vet. Med. 6 (1).
- Shaba P, Pandey NN, Sharma OP, Rao JR, Singh RK (2007). Comparative anti trypanosomal activity of *Terminalia chebula* dried fruits against *Trypanosoma evansi*. Planta Med. 73: 997-1034.
- Shaba P, Pandey NN, Sharma OP, Rao JR, Singh RK (2008). *In vitro* Trypanocidal and Cytotoxicity Effects of Methanolic Extract of *Vitex negundo* leaves against *Trypanosoma evansi*. The 13th Congress of the Federation of Asian Veterinary Associations. Pages 43-44.FAVA-OIE Joint Symposium on Emerging Diseases, Bangkok, Thailand.
- Sidwell RW, Hoffman JH (1997). Antiviral drug resistance. Res. Virol 148: 353-365.
- Stahl E (1969). Thin Layer Chromatography: A Laboratory Handbook. Springer, New York.
- Tyler VE (1982). The honest herbal. George F. Stickley Co., Philadelphia, PA.
- Williamson J, March JC, Scott-Finling JJ (1982). Drug synergy in experimental African trypanosomiasis. Tropenmedizin und Parasitologie 33: 76-82.
- Woo PTK (1971a). Evaluation of the haemataocrit centrifuge and other techniques for the field diagnosis of human trypanosomiasis and filariasis. J. Acta Trop. 28: 298-303.
- World Health Organization (2004). Anon; 2004 communicable Disease Surveillance and Response. WHO, Geneva.
- Young V, Schmitz V, Vanner-Santos MA, Lima APC.A, Lalmanach G, Juliano L., Gauthier F .and Scharfstein J (2000). Altered expression of cruzipain and a cathepsin B-like target in a *Trypanosoma cruzi* cell line displaying resistance to synthetic inhibitors of cysteine-proteinases. J. Mol. Biochem. and. Parasitol; 109: 47-59.